

Ownership Structure and Firm Performance: Global Evidence from 2000–2025¹

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Article Type / Makale Türü: Research Article / Araştırma Makalesi

Vol / Cilt 7 (Issue/Sayı 2) 2025:173-185

 10.5281/zenodo.18115072

Received/ Gönderilme: 15.11.2025

Revision / Revizyon: 15.12.2025

Accepted / Kabul: 29.12.2025

Cite as / Atıf: Atasel, O. Y., Şeker, Y. (2025). Ownership Structure and Firm Performance: Global Evidence from 2000–2025, Quantrade Journal of Complex Systems in Social Sciences, 7 (2), 173-185.

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18115072

Abstract

Ownership structure significantly influences who controls the flow of funds and how decisions are made. In other words, ownership structure reflects the firm's rights and the impact it has on managerial operations. The nature of ownership structure can influence firm performance directly or indirectly. Among the primary challenges facing the relationship between ownership structure and financial performance are performance conflicts between management and shareholders, agency issues, and the effectiveness of the corporate governance unit. This relationship has been addressed in the literature through the lens of different ownership types, such as institutional investor presence, family ownership, foreign capital ownership, and executive ownership. Furthermore, industry structure, market conditions, and structural adjustments at the level of ownership structure have also been significant factors in the power and direction of ownership structure on financial performance. The purpose of this study is to expand research studies covering the gap between ownership structure and firm performance between 2000 and 2025 through bibliometric analysis. For this purpose, a search was conducted in the Scopus database using the keywords “ownership structure, ownership concentration, ownership type, blockholder, controlling shareholder, insider ownership, family ownership, state ownership, foreign ownership, firm performance, financial performance, corporate performance, ROA, ROE, Tobin’s Q, profitability, market-to-book”, and the results were filtered to include only journal articles. The study analyzes publication trends by year, most cited studies, leading authors, influential journals, thematic focuses, and international collaboration networks.

Keywords: Ownership Structure, Firm Performance, Bibliometric Analysis.

Sahiplik Yapısı ve Firma Performansı: 2000–2025 Dönemine İlişkin Bir İnceleme

Öz

Sahiplik yapısı, işletmenin kontrolün kimde olduğunu ve stratejik kararların nasıl alındığına büyük ölçüde etki etmektedir. Başka bir ifadeyle sahiplik yapısı, yatırımcıların firmaya ilişkin haklarının ve yönetsel süreçler üzerindeki etkilerinin düzeyini göstermektedir. Sahiplik yapısının atfedilen özelliğinden dolayı firma performansı üzerinde doğrudan ya da dolaylı etkileri olabilmektedir. Sahiplik yapısı ve finansal performans arasındaki ilişkiyi açıklayan kavramların başında

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yönetim ile hissedarlar arasındaki çikaryayın çatışmaları, temsil (agency) sorunları ve kurumsal yönetim mekanizmalarının etkinliği gelmektedir. Söz konusu ilişki literatürde; kurumsal yatırımcı varlığı, aile sahipliği, yabancı sermaye payı ve yönetici sahipliği gibi farklı sahiplik türleri açısından ele alınmıştır. Ayrıca sektör yapısı, piyasa koşulları ve ülke düzeyindeki hukuki düzenlemeler de sahiplik yapısının finansal performans üzerindeki etkisinin gücünü ve yönünü belirleyen önemli faktörler olmuştur. Bu çalışmanın amacı, 2000–2025 yılları arasında sahiplik yapısı ile firma performansı arasındaki ilişkiyi araştıran çalışmalarını bibliyometrik analiz aracılığıyla incelemektir. Bu doğrultuda Scopus veri tabanında “sahiplik yapısı, sahiplik yoğunluğu, sahiplik türü, blok hissedar, kontrol hissedarı, içeriden bilgiye sahip sahiplik, aile sahipliği, devlet sahipliği, yabancı sahiplik, firma performansı, finansal performans, kurumsal performans, ROA, ROE, Tobin’in Q, karlılık, piyasa-defter değeri oranı” anahtar kelimeleriyle yapılan tarama yalnızca makalelerle sınırlandırılmış ve elde edilen yayınlar detaylı analizlere tabi tutulmuştur. Çalışmada yıllara göre yayın eğilimleri, en çok atıf alan çalışmalar, öne çıkan araştırmacılar, etkili dergiler, tematik alanlar ve uluslararası iş birliği ağları değerlendirilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sahiplik Yapısı, Finansal Performans, Bibliyometrik Analiz.

Introduction

The ownership structure is a crucial component of corporate governance that specifies the allocation of control inside firms and outlines the rights, duties, and incentives of various stakeholders. Jensen and Meckling (1976) assert that ownership encompasses the formalization of equity distribution and the mechanisms employed to ensure managerial oversight and alignment with shareholder interests. According to Fama and Jensen (1983), the ownership structure becomes a strategic factor that has direct and indirect effects on the performance of the organization. This process is accomplished through the allocation of capital and through the discretion and accountability of the management. Agency theory has historically dominated the literature, highlighting the conflicts that result from the separation of ownership and control. These conflicts can lead to agency costs, which hurt business performance (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). However, this perspective alone cannot adequately explain performance outcomes in various institutional issues. Aguilera and Crespi-Cladera (2016) contend that ownership structure is integrated within extensive governance systems influenced by national institutions, legal frameworks, and cultural norms. This approach has led to the development of complementary theories, such as stewardship theory, which posits that managers may serve as stewards of organizational objectives (Davis et al., 1997), and resource dependence theory, which interprets ownership as a strategic connection to external resources and legitimacy (Hillman et al., 2009). The impact of ownership structure is inherently dependent upon the situation. In developed economies with strong regulatory systems and effective capital markets, ownership may have a relatively insignificant impact on corporate performance (Demsetz & Villalonga, 2001). In emerging economies with weaker institutions and increased information asymmetries, ownership characteristics—such as state ownership, family involvement, or foreign investment—can substantially affect results (Abdallah & Ismail, 2017; Tran et al., 2025). State ownership is associated with performance inefficiencies due to political interference (Bhagat & Bolton, 2008), whereas foreign ownership may improve performance by introducing governance standards and expertise (Tran et al., 2025). Analyses at the firm level demonstrate differing impacts contingent upon ownership types. Anderson and Reeb (2003) demonstrated that, under specific situations, founding-family ownership leads to enhanced performance outcomes in S&P 500 businesses. On the contrary, concentrated ownership is not inherently advantageous, as it may entrench dominant shareholders and diminish accountability (Demsetz & Villalonga, 2001). Against this background, a clearer understanding of how the literature on ownership structure and corporate performance has evolved over time becomes necessary. Research on ownership structure and firm performance has expanded considerably over the past decades, with a strong emphasis on firm-level empirical evidence and meta-analytical evaluations. Much of this paper, however, remains anchored in particular datasets, country settings, or theoretical lenses. Consequently, the literature offers only a partial view of how research themes, geographical focus, and patterns of scholarly collaboration have evolved over time. To examine these broader dimensions, this study relies on a bibliometric analysis of peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2000 and 2025, drawing on data obtained from the Scopus database. The analysis considers ownership-related concepts such as ownership structure, blockholders, state, family, and

foreign ownership, together with commonly employed performance indicators including ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q. By analysing publication trends, identifying leading countries and institutions, mapping international collaboration networks, and tracing emerging research themes, the study offers a structured overview of the evolution of the ownership–performance literature.

1. Methodology

The empirical material analysed in this study consists of peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2000 and 2025 that address the relationship between ownership-related characteristics and firm performance. Bibliographic data were collected from the Scopus database, which was selected due to its broad coverage of journals in finance, economics, and corporate governance research. The search strategy was restricted to studies in which ownership-related concepts—namely ownership structure, ownership concentration, ownership type, blockholder, controlling shareholder, insider ownership, family ownership, state ownership, and foreign ownership—together with performance-related terms such as firm performance, financial performance, corporate performance, ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q, profitability, and market-to-book ratios appeared in the title, abstract, or keywords. Applying these criteria resulted in a final dataset comprising 3,171 journal articles. Prior to analysis, the dataset was screened to ensure consistency and reliability. Duplicate records were identified and removed, and entries with incomplete or missing bibliographic information were excluded. The cleaned dataset was then used for subsequent bibliometric analyses. Descriptive performance indicators, including publication output, citation structure, and source dynamics, were examined using the Bibliometrix package (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). In addition, network-based bibliometric analyses were conducted following the VOSviewer framework. These analyses focused on patterns of co-authorship, keyword co-occurrence, and institutional collaboration. The resulting network visualisations were further refined to enhance interpretability and ensure consistency in presentation.

2. Findings

The findings section details the insights obtained from the bibliometric analysis of studies focusing on the relationship between ownership structure and firm performance.

Figure 1. Number of Publications by Year

As shown in Figure 1, publications on ownership structure and firm performance were quite scarce in the early 2000s. Publications showed an upward trend between 2005 and 2009. However, the main increase occurred after 2014. By 2025, the highest number of publications had been made in that year. Between 2015 and 2019, publications in this field focused more on subtopics such as corporate governance, ownership intensity, family ownership, institutional investor behavior, and foreign capital. There has been an increase in publications since 2021. Particularly after the pandemic, publications have considered subtopics such as corporate governance structures, decision-making processes under uncertainty, and ownership changes. Publications on ownership structure and company performance have increased over the years, reflecting growing interest in this area. The volume of publications in this field is increasing daily, enriching both theory

and practice. Considering these circumstances, this field can be interpreted as an important area of research in the future.

Figure 2. Top Publishing Countries (2000-2025)

Figure 2 shows the countries with the highest number of publications on ownership structure and firm performance. According to this figure, the countries with the highest number of publications in this field are the United States (552 publications), China (465 publications), and the United Kingdom (298 publications). Among developing Asian countries, Indonesia, Malaysia, and India rank highest in this field. This indicates a growing academic interest in ownership structure and corporate governance in Asian countries. Furthermore, the rapid development of capital markets and transformations in corporate structures in these countries contribute to increased research on the subject. Among European countries, Spain and Italy rank higher than Germany and France, contributing more publications. The inclusion of Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Jordan from the Middle East in the ranking indicates growing interest in corporate governance research in that region as well. Türkiye appears in the ranking with 49 publications, indicating that a limited number of studies have been conducted in this field.

Figure 3. Top Institutions by Documents (2000-2025)

Figure 3 lists the institutions that published the most on ownership structure-firm performance between 2000 and 2025. Accordingly, the institutions that contributed the most publications were, in order: Universiti Utara Malaysia (37 publications), The Hong Kong Polytechnic University (27 publications), and College of Business, Universiti Utara Malaysia (23 publications). Looking at the top three institutions, the fact that they

are based in Malaysia and Hong Kong indicates a regional concentration in corporate governance research. The high ranking of leading institutions such as Università Bocconi from Italy, Peking University, Renmin University of China, and Shanghai University of Finance and Economics from China represents the strong presence of publications on ownership structure and firm performance within the Asia-Pacific academic community.

Figure 4. Authors with More than 5 Publications (2000-2025)

Figure 4 presents information on authors who contributed at least five publications on ownership structure-firm performance between 2000 and 2025. According to this information, the author with the highest number of publications in this field was Al-Najjar, B. (12 publications). This author was followed by Iwasaki, I. (9 publications), Hussainey, K., Kočenda, E., and Yoshikawa, T. (8 publications each). Al-Najjar, B.'s publications generally focused on the relationship between corporate ownership, management practices, and firm performance. Iwasaki, I.'s publications, on the other hand, focus on transition economies, institutions, and the impact of ownership structures on economic performance. Finally, the common research area of Hussainey, K., Kočenda, E., and Yoshikawa, T. covers topics directly related to ownership structure, such as corporate governance, financial reporting, management quality, and firm strategies.

Figure 5. Top 5 Subject Areas (2000-2025)

Figure 5 shows according to the Scopus subject area classification, publications related to ownership structure and firm performance are predominantly categorized under Business, Management, and Accounting (2,062 documents) and Economics, Econometrics, and Finance (1,740 documents), representing approximately 80% of the total output. Social Sciences (567), Decision Sciences (181), and Environmental Sciences (166) make a significant contribution. This distribution indicates that while the ownership structure-firm performance literature is inherently interdisciplinary, its analytical core remains firmly rooted in corporate governance and financial economics. The subject area distribution highlights the dominance of business and finance perspectives in the literature, complemented by contributions from adjacent disciplinary fields.

such as institutional investors, state ownership, bank performance, and emerging markets indicating that studies on investor types, state ownership, and the financial sector occupy an important place in the literature.

Figure 8. Overlay Map – Keywords evolution over time (2000–2025)

The overlay map shows the development of keywords used in ownership structure, ownership concentration, ownership type, blockholder, controlling shareholder, insider ownership, family ownership, state ownership, foreign ownership, firm performance, financial performance, corporate performance, ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q, profitability, market-to-book literature over the years. The color scale reflects the average publication years of the keywords. The map shows that fundamental concepts such as corporate governance, ownership structure, financial performance, and firm performance which are located closer to the center, belong to publications from the mid-term (2016–2018 tones). This reveals that these themes have long formed the core research axis in the literature. In contrast, the appearance of concepts such as state ownership, institutional investors, privatization, and bank performance in colors corresponding to the more recent period (2019–2021) shows that topics such as public ownership, the impact of institutional investors, and financial sector performance have gained greater importance in ownership structure discussions, particularly in recent years. On the other hand, themes such as family ownership, insider ownership, and board characteristics are concentrated in relatively older studies and stand out as well-established research areas in the literature.

Figure 9. Thematic Map

Figure 9 shows the thematic map reveals a clear structural organization of the intellectual landscape on ownership structure and firm performance. The upper-right quadrant (high centrality–high density) contains

the field's motor themes, where concepts such as corporate governance, ownership concentration, and firm performance cohere around robust internal linkages while also exhibiting strong connectivity to other themes. This indicates that these topics continue to function as the conceptual backbone of the literature. In contrast, the lower-right quadrant hosts the basic and transversal themes, including institutional ownership, managerial ownership, and capital structure, which show strong centrality but relatively lower density. These themes serve as methodological and theoretical anchors that support a wide range of empirical studies. The upper-left quadrant includes niche themes such as board-related constructs (board independence, board characteristics) that exhibit strong internal cohesion but limited external linkage. Their presence suggests the existence of specialized sub-domains with focused research communities. Lastly, the lower-left quadrant contains emerging (or possibly declining) themes, particularly those related to family ownership and ownership heterogeneity. Their low centrality and density indicate that, although they appear in the literature, they have not yet evolved into dominant or conceptually integrated research domains.

Institution Collaboration Network (min 3 pubs, edge ≥ 2)

Figure 10. Institution Collaboration Network

Figure 10 shows the collaborative relationships between institutions that have published at least three joint papers in the field of ownership structure and firm performance. The map reveals that institutional collaborations in the literature form regional clusters and that certain universities are located at the centre of the network. Several institutions appear close to the center of the network, including Universiti Utara Malaysia, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Xiamen University, Shanghai University of Finance and Economics, and Renmin University of China. These universities maintain a relatively large number of collaborative links, which points to their active involvement in joint research rather than isolated publication efforts. A prominent characteristic of the network is the concentration of institutions situated in Asia, particularly in Malaysia, China, and Indonesia, where collaborative links are markedly more prevalent. Universities from Europe and Oceania are also included in the network, although their connections are fewer and more scattered, often positioned away from the central clusters.

Figure 11. Country Collaboration Network (2000-2025)

Figure 11 shows the country collaboration network, revealing that the publications in the field of ownership structure and firm performance strongly cluster around international partnerships. The figure provides an opportunity to evaluate both productivity and collaboration intensity simultaneously, as node size represents publication volume and line thickness represents collaboration strength. China, the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, and Canada are at the centre of the network, possessing both high publication numbers and extensive international collaboration networks. This indicates that a significant portion of knowledge output in the literature is shaped around these countries. In the Asia-Pacific region, countries such as Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam, Taiwan, and South Korea have established strong connections with each other and with the central countries. This region shows a distinct concentration at the country level, as it does in the inter-institutional network. European countries (Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, Spain, France) have strong cooperation structures but remain in a more peripheral position compared to the central countries. Middle Eastern and North African countries (Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Egypt, Jordan, Tunisia) are part of the network but have more limited and regional collaborations.

Author Co-authorship Network (min 3 pubs, edge ≥ 2)

Figure 12. Author Coauthorship Network

Figure 12 shows the Author Co-authorship Network. The collaboration network does not follow a single, compact structure. Instead, links are dispersed across the literature, with activity concentrating around a limited

number of focal authors. Several researchers appear close to the centre of the network, including Hussainey, K., Tabash, M. I., Ting, I. W. K., Kočenda, E., Zeitun, R., and Firth, M. These authors are associated with repeated publication activity and maintain connections with multiple research groups, which places them in positions that connect otherwise separate parts of the network. The network structure also reveals the formation of regional research teams. Asia-centred working groups (Malaysia, China, Taiwan, etc.) in particular form distinct clusters and contribute significantly to the international literature through joint studies. Researchers based in Europe and the Middle East, on the other hand, operate on a relatively smaller scale but maintain strong internal ties. The spread of connections between authors across a wide geography indicates a highly internationalised collaborative structure in the field of research. However, the fact that the network consists of several medium-sized clusters rather than a central ‘super-core’ indicates that different research communities have developed in parallel in the literature.

Note: Only top keywords per period are shown; links connect keywords recurring across periods. Thickness scales with minimum frequency across the linked periods.

Figure 13. Thematic Evolution Map (2000–2025)

The thematic evolution map shown in Figure 13 reveals how research themes in ownership structure and firm performance literature changed between 2000 and 2025, and which concepts showed continuity. The thickness of the lines on the map indicates the frequency with which concepts recurred across periods. The main themes that have continued steadily over the three periods are corporate governance, ownership structure, firm performance, financial performance, and agency theory. Across different time periods, the literature does not show abrupt breaks in its core themes. Early work from the 2000–2010 period frequently addressed issues related to family firms, family ownership, and insider ownership. These topics continue to appear in later studies, although they are not always at the centre of attention. In subsequent years, the scope of the literature broadens, and references to institutional ownership, state ownership, corporate social responsibility, and emerging markets become more common alongside earlier firm-level concerns. Between 2014 and 2018, a noticeable number of studies focused on financial and governance-related topics, including ownership concentration, profitability, and capital structure. These concepts are also present in publications from the

2019–2025 period, suggesting that interest in governance and financial dimensions did not remain limited to a single phase of the literature. This trend indicates that the relationship between ownership structure and firm policies and financial outcomes is increasingly being addressed within more analytical and measurable frameworks. Generally the literature's fundamental themes are continued, while it can be said that more contemporary topics such as institutional investors, state ownership, sustainability and emerging markets have come to the fore, particularly in recent years.

3. Conclusion

This study comprehensively examined publications addressing the relationship between ownership structure and firm performance during the period 2000–2025, within a bibliometric analysis framework, and thus systematically revealed the developmental trends in the literature. The findings clearly reveal that ownership structure research has gained significant momentum over the past 20 years, with publication activity showing a strong increase, particularly since 2014. Evidently, this is directly related to the global change in corporate governance, the deepening of capital markets, and the diversification of investor priorities.

Moreover, the analysis results show that the United States, China, and the United Kingdom are clearly central to publication activity. An examination of the institutional distribution of the studies further reveals that universities in Malaysia, Hong Kong, and China have made significant contributions to the literature on ownership structures. This finding strongly confirms that the research field has shifted towards an Asia-Pacific-centred structure in recent years, and that academic institutions in the region are showing increasing attention to corporate governance issues.

In addition, keyword co-occurrence and thematic maps reveal that the literature has long been shaped around the axes of corporate governance, ownership structure, agency theory, and firm performance; these main themes have shown continuity throughout all periods. However, the research focus has diversified over time, and macro- and policy-oriented themes—such as institutional ownership, state ownership, emerging markets, and corporate social responsibility—have gained importance, particularly in recent years. This trend indicates that ownership structure research has strong links not only at the firm level but also with country governance models and regulation systems.

Similarly, international collaboration networks point to a highly globalised research environment at both the country and institutional levels. The fact that China, the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, and Canada are at the centre of the network with extensive connections indicates that research productivity in the literature is largely shaped around these countries. Additionally, the strong clustering of Asia-Pacific countries suggests that regional collaborations are becoming increasingly effective and influential.

In conclusion, bibliometric findings reveal that the literature on ownership structure and corporate performance has matured in terms of both theoretical framework and applied studies. Nevertheless, the rise in recent years of topics such as state ownership, sustainability, institutional investor behaviour, financial sector specifics, and differences in institutional structures in developing countries suggests that new research opportunities are emerging in the literature. In particular, increased data access, corporate transformation in emerging markets, and the spread of ESG-focused corporate governance suggest that the relationship between ownership structure and performance will likely be addressed through more interdisciplinary approaches in the future.

Taken together, the bibliometric findings suggest several directions for how the ownership structure–firm performance literature may be approached in future studies. Much of the existing research continues to rely on a limited set of performance indicators—most notably ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q—while other measures of firm outcomes appear far less frequently. In a similar vein, the thematic structure of the literature indicates that certain ownership settings receive sustained attention, whereas others remain comparatively marginal. Moreover, the collaboration patterns observed across countries and institutions also point to noticeable imbalances in research activity, which may limit the generalisability of performance-related conclusions.

Within this framework, the study brings together the historical development of the literature, its thematic organisation, and international collaboration structures to provide a clearer picture of how research on ownership structure and firm performance has evolved. By mapping these patterns, the analysis offers a structured reference point for future studies seeking to position new research questions within the existing body of knowledge.

Ethical Considerations of the Study

It is declared that the study was designed to realistically and ethically meet the needs, and that integrity was maintained in obtaining data, concluding the study, and publishing the results. Ethical committee approval was not required for this research. No research requiring ethics committee approval was conducted in this study.

Informed Consent

There was no need to obtain informed consent from individuals, as the study did not involve any procedures or interventions on human participants.

Author Contributions

Idea/Concept: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.; Design: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.; Supervision/Consultancy: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.; Resources: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.; Data Collection and/or Processing: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.; Analysis and/or Interpretation: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.; Literature Review: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.; Writing: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.; Critical Review: O.Y.A, Y.Ş.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflict of interest

Funding

The study did not receive any financial support from individuals or institutions.

Declarations

This study is revised and expanded version of the paper presented at the 6th BİLSEL International World Science and Research Congress held on 28-29 December 2024.

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